

ATHENA view of the highest-z X-ray extended jets

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Jetted QSOs observed in X-ray

3C273

Chandra

ROSAT - HRI

The **core emission**: Synchrotron + Inverse Compton (IC); possible seeds for the IC are sync photons (SSC) or AGN photons (EC).

The **extended emission**: two possible explanations:

- Inverse Compton with CMB (IC-CMB, Tavecchio+00, Celotti+01)
- Synchrotron by a second population

The 2 scenarios are different for jet composition, total energetics and physical parameters

EXTENDED EMISSION AT HIGH Z

The CMB photon density is $\propto (1+z)^4$; the interaction of jet electron with CMB photons is unavoidable

A basic prediction of the IC/CMB model is that the ratio $\text{jet Lum}_X / \text{Lum}_{\text{radio}}$ should increase with z

Sparse sample of extended jets at high z : Chandra observed 150 extended jets, mostly at $z < 1$, only a few at $z > 2$.

L_X/L_{radio} evolution

CMB is expected to affect the core unresolved emission too.

We compare the properties of two **blazar samples** :

(i) Caccianiga+19 sample: FSRQ at **4 <z< 5** from the CLASS survey

(ii) homogeneous BZCAT (Massaro+18) subsample **z ~ 1**

X/radio evolves with z, **consistently with IC-CMB** expectations

See caccianiga+19; ighina+19 ighina+21

Consistent with Wu+13, Zhu+19.

Radio-loud population density evolution

Several studies reported a *different evolution for the most-massive/luminous RL QSO from RQ population* ; with density peak at higher z .

This could be relevant in the understanding the relationship jet-spin-accretion of the SMBH

We found that this could be an **effect of the X/R evolution on the selection function** of the samples.

Two Extended jets at $z \sim 6$

- In 2021/2 two X-ray extended jets have been reported
- Potentially interesting to directly test the IC-CMB

banados+18, momjian+18 connor+21

belladitta+20, spingola +20, ighina+22

PSO J352.4034–15.3373 at z=5.8

jet $\sim 5\%$ of the core flux
 distance HS / core 8"
 ~ 8 photons collected in 265 ks
 chandra c.rate $\sim 3e-5$ (1 ph/10 hours ...)
 Chandra observation does not help ...

ATHENA WFI c.rate $\sim 3e-3$
 PSF core contamination :
 $\sim 3\%$ of the total PSF, 50% of the jet emission

PSOJ 0309+27 at $z=6.1$

The most distant blazar and X-ray extended source detected so far, discovered by combining PS with NVSS

Jet flux $\sim 10\%$ of the core
 distance jet-core $\sim 5''$
 chandra c.rate $\sim 2e-4$ c/s

belladitta+20,
 spingola +20,
 moretti+21
 ighina+22

PSOJ 0309+27 ATHENA simulation

ATHENA c.rate $\sim 1.3\text{e-}2$

core contamination :

$\sim 5\%$ of the total PSF, $\sim 50\%$ of the jet emission

PSOJ 0309+27 core variability

Two **significant soft flares** in the the core emission

Extremely **short time scale** (~ 1 hr)

Very soft photon index of the flares (2.6 ± 0.3), consistent with a BB ~ 3.0 KeV.

Possible interpretation: interaction between jet cold electron and AGN photons (bulk comptonization Begelman&Sikora+87, Celotti07)

Observational Strategy

Tens of blazars expected with LSST+EMU at $6 < z < 8$

Blazar are rare sources, not included in the surveys

Deep ATHENA **pointed observations** might reach 3 goals

- spectrum of the extended jets
- variability of the core unresolved emission
- overdensity

X-ray emission of QSOs extended jet is still to be understood. Discerning the radiation mechanism would be very important to constrain the composition and the physical properties of the systems.

Chandra observed a lot of extended objects, but only a few at high- z and with poor statistics. This leaves some important open questions.

The combination of good PSF with the very large effective area of ATHENA will significantly improve our knowledge of these objects, in synergy with the incoming optical/IR and radio facilities.

